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LAND PLANNING AS A SUPPORT FOR SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT BASED ON TOURISM: A CASE STUDY OF SLOVAK RURAL REGION

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Abstract

Current research details methodological framework for the land planning of the recreational activities based on ecologic approach. Human impacts on landscapes caused by touristic activities should be in accordance with sustainability level, i.e. without changing natural landscape elements, their function and processes, as well as environmental quality. Region of Štiavnické Bane in Slovakia represents a case study area that is completely under nature and landscape conservation. The methodological framework for the planning of recreational activities is based on the methodology of ecologic carrying capacity which is implemented by the Landscape ecological planning. The main result from this work is suitable tourism activities determined by the ecological approach. Methodological steps include spatial analysis, interpretation, evaluations and propositions which were suggested for recreational activities. The most suitable activities for winter periods are downhill skiing, cross-country skiing and winter tourism. For the summer period the best activities are the following ones: hiking, water sports and recreational activities linked to watering and sport fishing. The most suitable activities for the year-round period are service facilities and therapeutic recreational facilities. This sum of the activities represents the level of the land using that has not any negative environmental impact.

Key words: environmental management, land use planning, landscape management, nature-based tourism, sustainable development, sustainable tourism

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